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STYLISTIC PECULARITIES OF SPORT COMMENTATION

СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ СПОРТИВНОГО КОММЕНТИРОВАНИЯ

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Abstract. In this article the light is thrown to different stylistic devices that can be found in such genre as sport commentary. A special attention is paid to such stylistic devices as metaphor, metonymy, charactonyms, and simile that can be found in the speech of any football commentator and with a help of which commentator colors his speech and gives a possibility of the real presence to a viewer. Nowadays sport represents a very significant part of our life and with the help of mass media development sport acquires greater importance in our society. One can call football to be the famous and very popular kind of sport among people of all ages. A large number of football fans switch on their TV sets when their favorite football command emerges in a field. And there football commentator helps to establish intercourse between a viewer and sport event. During the match commentator explains in details all the events that take place in a field. A commentator gives a full picture of the football game and at the same time he entertains the viewers to keep their interest to the game. It is not easy as it may seem at first, as a commentator should possess rich vocabulary, and be a very intelligent and well-informed person not only to comment actions of football players but also to fill the pauses during the plain game.

Аннотация. С помощью средств массовой информации болельщики могут принять участие в футбольной игре и получить ощущение реального присутствия. В данной статье внимание обращено на различные стилистические приемы, которые можно найти в таком жанре, как спортивное комментирование. Особое внимание обращено на такие стилистические приемы как: метафора, метонимия, говорящие имена, сравнение, которые можно обнаружить в речи любого футбольного комментатора и с помощью которых комментатор окрашивает свою речь, давая телезрителям возможность реального присутствия на футбольном поле. В настоящее время спорт занимает значительное место в нашей жизни и с развитием средств массовой информации, спорт приобретает большое значение в обществе. Футбол представляет собой очень известный и популярный вид спорта среди людей всех возрастов. Большое количество футбольных фанатов включают их телевизоры, когда любимая футбольная команда появляется на поле. Футбольный комментатор помогает наладить связь между телезрителями и футбольным событием. Во время матча комментатор объясняет в деталях все события, которые происходят на футбольном поле. Комментатор подробно описывает футбольную игру и в то же время занимает телезрителей, чтобы сохранить их интерес к игре. Это нелегко, как может показаться сначала, так как комментатор должен иметь богатый запас слов, а также быть очень образованным и хорошо

информированным человеком, для того чтобы не только комментировать действия спортсменов, но также заполнять паузы во время игры.

Keywords: Sport commentation, stylistic devices, metaphor, metonymy, charactonyms, simile.

Ключевые слова: спортивное комментирование, стилистические приемы, метафора, метонимия, говорящие имена, сравнение.

The communication between a commentator and an audience is provided with the help of television. In this article the analysis is carried out at Russian and English football matches commentaries. Commentary is (from Latin — explanation, interpretation) one of the form of analytical material, explaining the meaning of an actual event [6, p.192]. Commentary is an opinion of phenomenon, situation, event, realized by a competent person, a specialist in a correspondent sphere. The commentary basis is considered to be an analyst's estimation, his own analysis of the current actions [12, p. 95]. In other words a commentator is a person who appeared to be a specialist in some or other knowledge field. Commentation genre takes a significant place, as with its help an analyst expresses his own relations and emotions, estimates advantages and disadvantages of the game and also can predict possible development of the football game. The commentation genre differs from the other genres with its possibility to analysis [12, p. 96]. Analyzing various football matches one can notice that every commentator analysis actions of the players and the all stadium in details, always giving them his own peculiar estimation. Even if actions, taking place on a TV set are rather clear for football aficionados, a commentator also forms and describes them without leaving them aside that always helps to keep the contact with audience and pays a significant attention to the actions which should be taken by the audience.

The audience represents a social group, united by the common interest. The main functions of sport commentary are considered to be, first of all, informational function as a commentator informs the football fans about the actions, taking place at the field, the second function is an estimative one as a commentator gives his own estimations to the football game, and the third function appears to be entertaining, as using this function a commentator also tries to make a match bright and memorable [9, p. 359]. Sport commentary is always a description of an event, which takes place in a real period of time. Sport analyst should completely deep into the football game he comments, giving the analytical analysis of the game peculiarities. The aim of commentary is maximally accurately give expression of the analyst's thoughts in combination with the commentator's feelings, inspired by the football game [8, p. 39]. Emotional component is a very peculiar feature of commentary, as with a help of which a commentator gives his own estimations and thoughts, through perspective of his individual perception interprets football game actions by his own. But emotional commentary is impossible without figures of speech, by means of them a commentator can not only express his feelings, but also give the estimation of various interesting moments, taking place during the football match. Such means of expression should be understood by the whole audience, as to make the audience the participant of the event, otherwise a commentator will lose his significance.

Figures of speech are used by a commentator to create an emotional coloring of the event, and also to interpret the mood of game participants [10, p. 61]. A great number of football expressions are based on metaphor and metonymy. Metaphor (from Greek metaphor — transfer) is a figure of speech represents denomination of a situation, phenomenon, or object by the word which usually denotes the other situation, phenomenon, or object, this denomination is based on some similarity in quality [2, p. 134]. With a help of metaphor a commentator can express his thoughts in a more definite way which helps to better understanding. Analyzing a number of football matches as in Russian, so in English one can distinguish some interesting examples of metaphor using, for instance, the examples from Russian commentation: “CSKA attacks again, trying on

handkerchief or even on a paper towel turns around his competitor”. At this example such expression as “on a handkerchief or even on a paper towel” acts as the metaphor, there the commentator Vladimir Stognienko tries to show the small space on which CSKA football command tries to beat its competitor. In the next instance the commentator with a help of metaphor describes kick: “But we know what a cannon and splitting kick has the footballer of Russian select team”. There the words cannon and splitting show the strength and power of the kick, the using of this metaphor intensifies the emotional perception. “Rostov realized his chance, Dmitri Poloz scored a goal to the checkroom”, there with a help of metaphor “scored a goal to the checkroom” one can understand that a goal was kicked by the Russian player in the dying seconds of the match. There the commentator also emphasizes the skill and professionalism of the player, how he could kick a goal in the latest seconds of the first time. In the next instance, “And omnipresent Gzinnyak kicks the ball into goalposts”. The commentator Victor Gusev used the word “omnipresent” to show that the football player Gzinnyak always appears in appropriate time and in appropriate place. The following examples of metaphor are taken from English commentation where the metaphor is also very actual: “As Liverpool continues to open the door to the second goal”. The metaphor “to open the door to the second goal” shows how fast and easy football command “Liverpool” kicks its second goal. There can be observed the following examples of metaphor in sport commentation: “So they are chasing the ball, rather than encourage the others to make pass”, in this instance the commentator uses the word “chase” to show how strongly the players try to possess the ball. “They just need in some belief and need in some injection of confidence”, there the “injection of confidence” serves as metaphor, and using it the analyst wants to pay audience attention to uncertainty of the football command. The next instance: “It is a big throw which is occupying two “Palace” defenders and Okazaki sneaking between them”, there with a help of metaphor the commentator shows how the player Okazaki tries to go between two defenders without being noticed. According to the above mentioned instances, it can be clearly observed here how a metaphor intensifies emotional perception and helps to a better understanding of the actions, taking place during the game.

Metonymy is a figure of speech, based on the title transfer from one object to the other one, on the ground of their similarity. As one can see metonymy has some kind of logical connection, while metaphor is based on objects resemblance [2, p.136]. Some examples of metonymy can also be found as in Russian, so in English commentary. For instance, “Rostov very aggressively comes forward”, there Rostov is used not to define a city, but to define players, entering the football command named “Rostov”. “Let’s see how Ural will react”, there it is also can be seen that the commentator defines the players of the football command Ural as a united body, using metonymy. In the following instance: “Certainly it was an unpleasant surprise for the bench”, there under the word bench the commentator means the substitutes, sitting on their bench. The same situation occurs in English commentary, where metonymy is also often used, and it can be seen in the next instance, “Manchester opens the score”, as the commentator calling the place means the football players, entering this command. In the following instance, “The stadium lends support to Oscar now”, a bright example of metonymy can be observed as commentator uses the word stadium to denote the people sitting on it. “Chelsea comes out and plays at another level and with a high tempo”, at this example the analyst also using the word Chelsea denotes the all players who considered to be in this football command. Thus, it can be observed that metonymy is rather often used in sport commentary and the most widespread metonymy type according to the instances found is when the place title is used to denote people situating there.

Simile also appears to be a significant mean, which can be found in every football commentary. Simile is a juxtaposition of one subject with the other one, basing on their similarity. Simile also can be expressed as by a word-combination, so even by the whole sentence [2, p.141]. Simile can be easily recognized in the next sentence: “We had luck to see him in reality, he is just like a real cupboard, he is a huge forward”. So “he is just like a real cupboard” serves in this sentence as a comparison, a famous forward is compared with a cupboard for audience

to understand that he is tall and wide-shouldered man. The following instance: “This was like a hockey episode, in other words a power body blow”, there in the word-combination “a hockey episode” a commentator compares a power body blow with a hockey technique. The next example is considered to be very curious: “Meanwhile real “Quentin Tarantino” took place on the field, one more yellow card”. It can be seen there that a proper noun of a famous stage director is mentioned to compare a genre of his films with the situation, taking place on the field. The following example is taken from the match “Manchester city vs Tottenham”: “But it looks like mission is impossible, feels like mission is impossible, but most of us believe in tonight”, there the situation on a field, the mood of the team is compared with title of the film “Mission: Impossible”. In the next example, “Fellaini is just a big guy, he is just like a Hulk”, there the football player is compared with a comics hero “Hulk”, as he is a very high and strong man. Thus, as it can be seen from the above mentioned examples, simile can often be noticed in a sport commentary, as it attach very emotional coloring to the commentary, making it livelier and clear.

Analyzing the speech of football commentators during the matches one can notice that one of the significant stylistic peculiarities of football sport commentary appears to be charactonyms. Charactonyms are given for some peculiar special features as in appearance, so in behavior of a sportsman or derivation from a surname. For instance, Wayne Mark Rooney an English football player and also the captain of the football command “Manchester United” got the charactonym “Shrek” mainly because of his formal resemblance with this personage. The other instance, based on formal resemblance is charactonym “El nino” which is translated from Spanish as a “baby” and belongs to Fernando Jose Torres, this nickname the football player got also because of his young face expression and maybe also because of his early talent revelation. Bastian Schweinsteiger got the charactonym “Swine” according to the derivation from his surname, as the first part of it Schwein is translated from German as swine. The same situation is occurred with the English footballer Frank James Lampard, he also got his nickname “Lamp-post” or “Lamp”, as his surname is concordant with the word lamp. Sergei Ovchinnikov is a Russian goal-keeper was called as a “Boss” because of his sharp disposition during the games. Also it is worth mentioning that Stuart Pearce an English footballer got the nickname “Madman” as he possessed a very impetuous temper. As it can be noticed sport commentary is impossible without charactonyms as they give very quick characteristic of the football players, coloring commentation and making it livelier and merrier, they come into the sport history.

To conclude, sport commentary is considered to be a significant type of reporting, as football game became nowadays a very popular and weighty kind of sport. The main point of the genre sport commentary is to present the football game in a development, intelligently reflect event’s dynamics. With the help of such figures of speech as metaphor, metonymy, simile and charactonym the commentator involves the audience, making commentary bright, witty, sometimes cheerful and sometimes serious and crucial. Using the above mentioned figures of speech the analyst explains all the actions on a field and at the same time gives his own characteristics to the game, based on his knowledge and experiences, making all the viewers believe in it.

In article used video material of football game (CSKA vs Rostov, 2016; Chelsea vs Manchester, 2016; French vs Russia, warm-up match, 2016; Manchester City vs Tottenham, 2016; Crystal Palace vs Leicester City, 2016; Southampton vs Chelsea, 2016; Barcelona vs Arsenal, 2016).

Nicknames of football players available at: http://rusfan.ru/posts/112824/prozvischa_futbolistov.

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